

“Their Finest Hour” Speech – Winston Churchill’s Enlightening Radio Broadcast during Britain’s “Darkest Hour”

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7463128

**Davian VLAD,
Assistant Professor, PhD, CCCSEM, University of Craiova, Romania**

Abstract: Winston Churchill (1874 - 1965) proved to be the right choice as Prime Minister when he replaced the hesitant Neville Chamberlain in the “darkest hour” of Europe. The continent had been invaded by the raging Nazi forces and the last hope for the final victory was Great Britain, after the resounding fall of France. That was the crucial moment when Churchill stepped in and addressed a masterful speech to the MPs in the House of Commons and the nation at the BBC radio in order to urge people to get ready for the terrible confrontation with Adolf Hitler’s frightening army. The acclaimed speech known as “Their Finest Hour” was a brilliant piece of oratory which revived the hope that the brutal war can be eventually won by the Allies.

Key words: Winston Churchill, World War II, speech, BBC, Battle of Britain

Winston Churchill became the Prime Minister of Great Britain in May 1940, replacing Neville Chamberlain while leading a national coalition meant to rule the country during a turbulent period which turned out to be nothing but a new World War. He proved to be a tenacious, skillful, intelligent and resilient politician who managed to lead the nations of the British Empire throughout a horrific conflagration that took more than 50 million lives and cast a long shadow over the decades to come, with consequences that are still to be observed today. Winston Churchill came to power after Neville Chamberlain lost the support of the Conservative Party in the House of Commons and resigned on May 10, 1940. Chamberlain could not coagulate a majority anymore and assemble himself a national government, being considered a reluctant politician who repeatedly believed Adolf Hitler’s deceitful commitments, unable to firmly take a stand against a dictator whose unconcealed ambitions were to subjugate other nations and conquer other countries in order to acquire the “living space” (*Lebensraum*) for “his” German people. Thus Chamberlain was replaced by a revived Churchill who, in the 1920s and especially 1930s, had managed to restore his reputation shattered during the World War I, in 1915, when, as First Lord of the Admiralty, was widely considered guilty for the disastrous Dardanelles naval campaign and the subsequent landings on Gallipoli which sustained tremendous losses. And this appointment agreed by most of the political forces of the UK would prove more than inspired, Winston Churchill being not only a skilled and determined leader, but also a master of

motivation and inspiration through his magnificent oratorical talent, a true man of both deeds and words.

His several memorable speeches (such as “Blood, Toil, Tears and Sweat”, “We Shall Fight on the Beaches”, “The Few” and, of course, “Their Finest Hour”) were so powerful and inspirational that would be credited “with galvanising national spirit and helping to inspire eventual victory”¹. Although he later said that they “were only words”, these so important speeches showed that words sometimes are more powerful than guns. And his mastery of delivering thoughts and ideas would place Churchill after the war into the perfect position to carefully review and manage his legacy, as David Reynolds notices in what he calls “the battle for history”: “(...) Churchill had dominated the field for a quarter century - through speeches and deeds in wartime and, even more, by what he wrote afterward. And he must surely have known, as he finally slipped away, that he had won the immortality he craved. In death, as in life, Winston Churchill continues to glow. He remains in command of history”². Reynolds considers that the two facets of Churchill’s personality significantly contributed to the perpetuation of the myth: “Churchill waged the Second World War twice over: as Prime Minister steering his country from disaster in 1940 to victory in 1945, and again as the conflict’s principal historian, with six volumes of memoirs published over the subsequent decade. The saga of his premiership is celebrated, the story of his war memoirs virtually unknown, yet Churchill the historian has shaped our image of Churchill the leader. As he liked to say when locked in wartime controversy, ‘I shall leave it to history, but remember that I shall be one of the historians’. No other war leader performed such a double act”³.

These extraordinary skills that empowered him with almost infallible rhetorical weapons were developed in decades, Martin Gilbert emphasizes, as Winston Churchill wrote enormously for all of his life: “Throughout his six decades in the public eye and in public life, he understood and wielded the power of words. In his speeches, books, and newspaper and magazine articles, he expressed his feelings and laid out his vision for the future. From his first experiences of war between 1895 and 1900, his vivid narrative style and thoughtful reflections were read with fascination in Britain and beyond. While still in his twenties, he was a much sought-after speaker in Britain and the United States”⁴.

“Their Finest Hour” was the third major speech Winston Churchill addressed to the MP’s in the House of Commons at first and, subsequently, to the nation on the radio. Usually, his speeches were presented first in front of the representatives and later, on the same day, recorded in the BBC studios. “Blood, Toil, Tears and Sweat” was given on May 13, 1940, three days after the

¹ Churchill: “Their finest hour”, <https://www.bbc.co.uk/teach/school-radio/history-ks2-world-war-2-clips-churchill-their-finest-hour/z7nc382>, accessed June 20, 2022

² David Reynolds, *In Command of History: Churchill Fighting and Writing the Second World War*, Random House, 2005, p.689

³ Ibid., p.8

⁴ Martin Gilbert, *Churchill: The Power of Words - His remarkable life recounted through his writings and speeches*, Bantam Press, 2012, p.7

start of the Battle of France, “We Shall Fight on the Beaches” on June 4, right after the miraculous Dunkirk evacuation, and “Their Finest Hour” on June 18, a few days before the inevitable surrender of France to the Nazis (on June 16, the French authorities demanded an armistice after the heavy losses suffered during the devastating *Blitzkrieg* unleashed by Hitler on May 10). The ardent speech lasted for 36 minutes and was enthusiastically received by most politicians and the entire nation who were asked by their leader to prepare for the Battle of Britain, now that the Battle of France was all but over.

As mentioned before, the famous speech was initially presented to the MPs who warmly received the manifesto for resistance against the inevitable Hitler’s attack on Great Britain. Later on, although Churchill was obviously exhausted, as King George VI himself noted in his diary after meeting the Prime Minister at Buckingham Palace following the speech, he went to BBC in order to address to the people through radio waves. And the national reaction was also swift and passionate, but some of those who had taken part in the session at the House of Commons noticed that his oratorical performance during the radio broadcast was not as powerful as earlier that day. An observation that Andrew Roberts considers to be not exactly accurate, especially from a subsequent perspective: “When Harold Nicolson at the Ministry of Information ‘bullied’ Churchill into reprising the speech that evening in a radio broadcast, which Churchill did not want to do as he was so busy, Nicolson recorded, ‘he just sulked and read his House of Commons speech over again. Now, as delivered in the House of Commons, that speech was magnificent, especially the concluding sentences. But it sounded ghastly on the wireless. All the great vigour he put in it seemed to evaporate.’ Perhaps Nicolson was right and it was less powerful than the original delivery, but that is certainly not the impression one gets hearing those sublime words on the recorded wireless version today”⁵. It’s exactly what Martin Gilbert also thinks, but with a slight twist: “Churchill repeated this speech over the radio four hours later. He was tired, and to those who had heard it earlier in the Commons it sounded much less convincing in its broadcast form; but to those who heard it for the first time as they sat around their wireless sets, it was an inspiration. These were ‘only words’, he later reflected. (...) He knew that ‘Rhetoric was no guarantee of survival’”⁶.

⁵ Andrew Roberts, *Churchill: Walking with Destiny*, Penguin Books, 2018, pp.635-636

⁶ Martin Gilbert, *Churchill: A Life*, Pimlico, 2000, p.664

Photo: www.bbc.co.uk

The process of writing and revising the text is fascinating. As usual, Winston Churchill continuously revisited the speech and made even last-minute changes, just moments before delivery, as an examination of papers held at Cambridge University in 2010 revealed ahead of the 70th anniversary of the Battle of Britain. Allen Packwood, archives director at the Churchill Archives Centre, was impressed by the work Churchill put into early drafts and the magnificent final version: "The page is covered with his handwritten annotations in red and blue ink. It highlights how much care and attention Churchill put into this speech. He knew how much was riding on this. The country was facing a huge national crisis. France had capitulated and Britain was facing the prospect of attack and invasion. (...) You can imagine him sitting on the front bench of the House of Commons spotting an error and making a quick change. (...) I think there is a big danger in this day and age of Churchill assuming a purely iconic status. What you can see here is his self-belief, his determination, his humanity, that leads us on from the dark days of 1940 to final victory in 1945. There's nothing quite like seeing the piece of paper that Churchill signed or the page that Churchill had in his hand when he delivered that amazing climax to his finest hour speech"⁷. A display of exquisite eloquence that would contribute to invigorating the morale of a nation, as historian Max Arthur states as well: "This is a colossal speech, the way he's evolved it, thought it through, realising more than any other Prime Minister before him just what impact this would have on the nation"⁸.

Although Winston Churchill wrote his speeches himself, or dictated them, as Prime Minister he was surrounded by plenty of counselors, advisors, collaborators, members of staff that were willing to help him develop the texts that would be presented to the representatives and the nation. So even if he was the one to decide what would stay and what would be taken out of the text, he was receptive to the suggestions proposed by his colleagues, Richard Toye writes: "The romantic image of Churchill as a lone genius conjuring masterly speeches out of the ether is misleading. It is true that he wrote them himself, but he did so as part of a collaborative process.

⁷ Churchill changed 'finest' speech in World War II, <https://www.bbc.com/news/10358511>, June 19, 2010, accessed July 2, 2022

⁸ Ibid.

Colleagues and officials supplied him with information and suggestions, and his drafts (which frequently reflected this advice) were often circulated within Whitehall for comment. It was not unusual for Churchill to accept recommendations that particular passages or sentences should be toned down or eliminated. This can be illustrated with evidence from the speech-writing files in the Churchill Papers, a neglected but valuable source. The files include original drafts, often with handwritten amendments, as well as related information and correspondence. In combination with contemporary diaries and memoirs - as well as the resources of the National Archives at Kew - these files allow us to reconstruct the drafting process. This allows us new insights into the origins of famous passages and phrases. It also reveals the bureaucratic sensitivities and political pressures that combined to shape Churchill's statements. It also reminds us of his and his colleagues' ever-present awareness that a misplaced phrase or sentence - or indeed a tactless omission - could have serious diplomatic or even military repercussions, or adverse consequences for public opinion"⁹.

Photo: winstonchurchill.org

Churchill started his spirited speech with a retrospective of the Battle of France, praising the formidable rescue operation in Dunkirk and the sacrifice of the British soldiers from the

⁹ Richard Toye, *The Roar of the Lion. The Untold Story of Churchill's World War II Speeches*, Oxford University Press, 2013, p.13

Expeditionary Force and their French allies, but bemoaning the reduced number of divisions Britain could deploy across the Channel in order to help French Army fight against the Germans:

“Our Army and 120,000 French troops were indeed rescued by the British Navy from Dunkirk but only with the loss of their cannon, vehicles and modern equipment. This loss inevitably took some weeks to repair, and in the first two of those weeks the battle in France has been lost. When we consider the heroic resistance made by the French Army against heavy odds in this battle, the enormous losses inflicted upon the enemy and the evident exhaustion of the enemy, it may well be the thought that these 25 divisions of the best-trained and best-equipped troops might have turned the scale. However, General Weygand had to fight without them. Only three British divisions or their equivalent were able to stand in the line with their French comrades. They have suffered severely, but they have fought well. We sent every man we could to France as fast as we could re-equip and transport their formations”¹⁰.

As a trenchantly remark about the fate of France (“What General Weygand called the Battle of France is over”¹¹) left no room for hope regarding their allied country, Churchill focused on preparing his fellow citizens for the worse, but without risking to cause panic, instead making everyone visualize the danger ahead and the perspective of fighting hard to defend their homeland:

“The disastrous military events which have happened during the past fortnight have not come to me with any sense of surprise. Indeed, I indicated a fortnight ago as clearly as I could to the House that the worst possibilities were open; and I made it perfectly clear then that whatever happened in France would make no difference to the resolve of Britain and the British Empire to fight on, if necessary for years, if necessary alone”¹².

“Therefore, in casting up this dread balance-sheet and contemplating our dangers with a disillusioned eye, I see great reason for intense vigilance and exertion, but none whatever for panic or despair. During the first four years of the last war the Allies experienced nothing but disaster and disappointment. That was our constant fear: one blow after another, terrible losses, frightful dangers. Everything miscarried. And yet at the end of those four years the morale of the Allies was higher than that of the Germans, who had moved from one aggressive triumph to another, who stood everywhere triumphant invaders of the lands into which they had broken. During that war we repeatedly asked ourselves the question: How are we going to win? and no one was able ever to answer it with much precision, until at the end, quite suddenly, quite unexpectedly, our terrible foe collapsed before us, and we were so glutted with victory that in our folly we threw it away”¹³.

¹⁰ Winston S. Churchill, *Never Give In! Winston Churchill's Speeches*, Bloomsbury, 2013, p.261

¹¹ *Ibid.*, p.270

¹² *Ibid.*, p.263

¹³ *Ibid.*, p.270

Winston Churchill then made a profound analysis of what may lay ahead for Great Britain, taking into consideration all the possible scenarios for the inevitable war with the Nazis:

“(…) it seems to me that as far as seaborne invasion on a great scale is concerned, we are far more capable of meeting it today than we were at many periods in the last war and during the early months of this war, before our other troops were trained, and while the BEF had proceeded abroad. Now, the Navy have never pretended to be able to prevent raids by bodies of 5,000 or 10,000 men flung suddenly across and thrown ashore at several points on the coast some dark night or foggy morning. The efficacy of sea power, especially under modern conditions, depends upon the invading force being of large size. It has to be of large size, in view of our military strength, to be of any use. If it is of large size, then the Navy have something they can find and meet and, as it were, bite on”¹⁴.

“This brings me, naturally, to the great question of invasion from the air, and of the impending struggle between the British and German Air Forces. It seems quite clear that no invasion on a scale beyond the capacity of our land forces to crush speedily is likely to take place from the air until our Air Force has been definitely overpowered. In the meantime, there may be raids by parachute troops and attempted descents of airborne soldiers. We should be able to give those gentry a warm reception both in the air and on the ground, if they reach it in any condition to continue the dispute”¹⁵.

“There remains, of course, the danger of bombing attacks, which will certainly be made very soon upon us by the bomber forces of the enemy. It is true that the German bomber force is superior in numbers to ours; but we have a very large bomber force also, which we shall use to strike at military targets in Germany without intermission. I do not at all underrate the severity of the ordeal which lies before us; but I believe our countrymen will show themselves capable of standing up to it, like the brave men of Barcelona, and will be able to stand up to it, and carry on in spite of it, at least as well as any other people in the world”¹⁶.

And then the grand finale that, as Andrew Roberts concludes, “will be remembered as long as the English language is spoken”¹⁷, an inspirational appeal addressed by Winston Churchill to his fellow citizens who should get ready for the titanic battle with the Evil in order to save the civilization as we know it:

“I expect that the Battle of Britain is about to begin. Upon this battle depends the survival of Christian Civilization. Upon it depends our own British life, and the long continuity of our institutions and our Empire. The whole fury and might of the enemy must very soon be turned on us. Hitler knows that he will have to break us in this Island or lose the war. If we can stand up to him, all Europe may be free and the life of the world may move forward into broad, sunlit

¹⁴ Winston S. Churchill, *Never Give In! Winston Churchill's Speeches*, Bloomsbury, p.265

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, p.266

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p.268

¹⁷ Andrew Roberts, *Churchill: Walking with Destiny*, Penguin Books, 2018, pp.635-636

uplands. But if we fail, then the whole world, including the United States, including all that we have known and cared for, will sink into the abyss of a new Dark Age made more sinister, and perhaps more protracted, by the lights of perverted Science. Let us therefore brace ourselves to our duties, and so bear ourselves that, if the British Empire and its Commonwealth last for a thousand years, men will still say ‘This was their finest hour’”¹⁸.

REFERENCES

Churchill, Winston S., *Never Give In! Winston Churchill's Speeches*, selected and edited by his grandson Winston S. Churchill, Bloomsbury, 2013

French, David, *Raising Churchill's Army: The British Army and the War Against Germany, 1919–1945*, Oxford University Press, 2000

Gilbert, Martin, *Churchill: A Life*, Pimlico, 2000

Gilbert, Martin, *Churchill: The Power of Words - His remarkable life recounted through his writings and speeches*, 200 readings selected, edited and introduced by Martin Gilbert, Bantam Press, 2012

Jefferys, Kevin, *The Churchill Coalition and Wartime Politics, 1940–1945*, Manchester University Press, 1995

Reynolds, David, *In Command of History: Churchill Fighting and Writing the Second World War*, Random House, 2005

Roberts, Andrew, *Churchill: Walking with Destiny*, Penguin Books, 2018

Toye, Richard, *The Roar of the Lion. The Untold Story of Churchill's World War II Speeches*, Oxford University Press, 2013

www.bbc.com

www.winstonchurchill.org

¹⁸ Winston S. Churchill, *Never Give In! Winston Churchill's Speeches*, Bloomsbury, 2013, pp.270-271